

Lorentz covariant formulation of the Navier-Stokes equations by Laplace-Beltrami differential operators

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Abstract

Though the Navier-Stokes equations of fluid mechanics have proven useful in multiple disciplines of physics and engineering, they are incapable of describing flows where relativistic effects are present due to their Galilean invariance. For a Navier-Stokes equation set to be mathematically capable of modeling relativistic effects on the temporal evolution of its velocity field in curved space, all of its differential operators must instead exhibit Lorentz covariance. Many attempts have been made at formulating a theory of viscous relativistic fluid mechanics, but none have emphasized Lorentz covariance. This work therefore seeks to construct a Lorentz covariant version of the Navier-Stokes model of fluid motion so as to support relativistic viscous flows. To accomplish this task, the Galilean invariant gradient, divergence, Laplacian, and material derivative operators present in the Navier-Stokes equations are reconstructed in terms of the covariant derivative operator for curved space. The velocity and external force fields are also modeled as four-vectors to capture the effects of time dilation and length contraction on turbulent flow patterns, which helps to properly account for the relativistic scaling and skewing of important observed phenomena such as temporal mixing scales and Komolgorov microscales.

1 Introduction

The Navier-Stokes equations (1-2) have been the cornerstone of classical fluid mechanics for two centuries. They relate the velocity $\mathbf{u}$, pressure P_0 , and density $\rho_0 \geq 0$ of a fluid with kinematic viscosity $\nu \geq 0$ and second viscosity $\zeta \geq 0$ in the presence of an external force $\mathbf{F}$ at the most general level allowed by Newtonian mechanics. Though they have proven invaluable in engineering applications despite their complexity and intractability, their foundational assumption of a Galilean invariant stress field [1] and a Cartesian control volume has hampered the extension of their scope to scenarios whose relativistic effects are significant. It is also possible for (1-2) to model the relativistic impossibility of superluminal flow velocity. Because general and special relativity model spacetime as a differentiable manifold and conserve mass and energy, it is at least possible on a philosophical level to construct a system of PDEs similar to (1-2) which address these contradictions between the Navier-Stokes model and known relativistic facts. This work is intended to reconcile the Navier-Stokes model with the modern findings of general and special relativity.

$$\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = \frac{\partial\mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} - \frac{\nabla P_0}{\rho_0} + \nu \nabla \cdot \left(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T - \frac{2\nu}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{I} \right) + \zeta \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{u}) = -\frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

The section of (1-2) in which the assumption of Galilean invariance wields the most influence is their viscous terms since the viscous effects on a flow are a function of its internal shear stresses. This relationship between shear stresses and viscous effects is assumed to be linear and is modeled by the Laplacian operator [2]. Since the mathematical capability that should be added to (1-2) to properly model relativistic effects is at least Lorentz covariance, and the Laplacian is Galilean invariant but not Lorentz covariant, another vector differential operator should be sought which is heuristically closest to the Laplacian operator while remaining mathematically sound. Unlike Galilean invariant systems which assume the absoluteness of both space and time, Lorentzian or special relativistic systems incorporate the relative dilation of time and contraction of length at high velocities [3]. General relativistic systems also incorporate the effects of curved spacetime in a Lorentzian context. In this work, we seek a fluid mechanical model of both. While many such differential operators are known, the operator most similar to the Laplacian operator which also supports the demands of both special relativistic changes in space and time dimensions and general relativistic curvature of spacetime is generally understood to be the Laplace-Beltrami operator [4].

2 Literary review

The work done thus far to produce a theory of fluid motion in curved space is varied in specificity and scope. Large-scale attempts to recast (1-2) in Lorentz covariant or invariant form do not appear to exist as of this writing, however, there has been extensive work done on building fairly general theories of nonrelativistic flows in curved spacetime. Many such works contribute generalizations of the underlying mathematics to support other field theories [5] such as quantum field theory in curved space, which is considered by many to be a necessary stepping stone towards a "theory of everything." A relativistic version of the simpler Euler equations, which correspond to (1-2) for $\nu = 0$ [6] is well-known, as are many exact solutions of the Einstein field equations which make use of the notion of a perfect fluid [7]. Other, more specific, attempts at establishing a link between the Einstein field equations and the Navier-Stokes equations have been made recently. It has been shown [8] that embedding a timelike hypersurface in an Einstein geometry of one dimension greater than said hypersurface and then imposing a Petrov type I condition and a certain restriction on a Hamiltonian operator causes the Einstein field equations governing that hypersurface to reduce to the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations wherein $\frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial(\dots)} = \zeta = 0$, confirming the well-known observations [9] that excitations of a black hole's event horizon resemble that of a fluid, and that the Einstein field equations themselves resemble (1-2) when projected onto null surfaces including black hole event horizons, albeit with the material derivative replaced with a Lie derivative. The latter case has been found to reduce identically to (1-2) in the limiting case of extremal spacetime entropy density [10]. Despite this plethora of intimate knowledge of the deep-seated mathematical and physical connections between general relativity and Newtonian fluid mechanics, there still exists the need of a fully Lorentz covariant theory of viscous fluid motion which approaches Galilean invariance (1-2) when the metric tensor approaches that of Cartesian space and all time is absolute.

3 Galilean invariance and Lorentz covariance

In order to begin an analysis of Lorentzian fluid mechanics in light of a known theory (1-2) of Galilean invariant fluid mechanics, we must first provide formal definitions of Galilean invariance and Lorentz covariance.

3.1 The Galilean transformation

The Galilean transformation (3) relates the coordinates of two reference frames moving at a constant relative velocity v along the x_1 -axis [11]. If the domain M of a vector field $\mathbf{v}$ equals its own Galilean transform at all points $(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M$, and $M = \mathbb{R}^4$, then $\mathbf{v}$ is said to be Galilean invariant. The pressure and velocity fields which together constitute the solution of (1-2) are assumed to be Galilean invariant in their derivation since Newtonian mechanics lay at the frontier of theoretical physics at the time (1-2) were discovered.

$$(x'_0, x'_1, x'_2, x'_3) = (x_0, x_1 - vx_0, x_2, x_3) \quad (3)$$

3.2 The Lorentz transformation

Similar to (3), the Lorentz transformation (4) relates the coordinates of two reference frames moving at a constant relative velocity v along the x_1 -axis. The key addition is a parameter γ known as the Lorentz factor which serves to protect against causal paradoxes by setting an upper limit $c > 0$ on the propagation of information. The consequence of this limit is that $v < c$ everywhere. In the physical universe, c equals the speed of light. When $v = 0$, the Lorentz transformation reduces to the Galilean transformation, implying that (3) is a special case of (4) for small v . Indeed, γ is only practically relevant for $v > \frac{c}{10}$ [12].

If the domain M of a vector field $\mathbf{v}$ equals its own Lorentz transformation at all points $(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M$, and M is a pseudo-Riemannian manifold with metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ whose line element is denoted ds (5), and metric signature $S \in \{[3, 1], [1, 3]\}$, then M is said to be a Lorentzian manifold [13]. If $\mathbf{v}$ is defined on a Lorentzian manifold and any Lorentz transforms do not change its components, then $\mathbf{v}$ is said to be Lorentz invariant. If they transform in a well-defined way, then $\mathbf{v}$ is said to be Lorentz covariant. Spacetime is always modeled as a Lorentzian manifold in both general and special relativity. In the context of this work, we seek a momentum conservation equation similar to (1) and a continuity equation similar to (2) which are Lorentz covariant in the same way (1-2) are Galilean invariant and provide an accurate description of fluid mechanics on any Lorentzian manifold. The stricter condition of Lorentz invariance is not feasible for a theory of fluid mechanics because identical turbulent flow patterns cannot be expected from all directions in which a Lorentz transform can be calculated. Even the metric tensor itself is Lorentz covariant but not invariant.

$$(x'_0, x'_1, x'_2, x'_3) = \left(\gamma \left(x_0 - \frac{vx_1}{c^2} \right), \gamma(x_1 - vx_0), x_2, x_3 \right), \quad \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (4)$$

$$g_{\mu\nu} : \left[(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M \times (\mu, \nu) \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,3]}^2 \right] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{00} & g_{01} & g_{02} & g_{03} \\ g_{10} & g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{20} & g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{30} & g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$ds = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 (g_{ij})^2 dx_i^2 dx_j^2} \quad (5)$$

4 Tensor calculus in curved space and relativistic flow properties

The formulation of (1-2) is in terms of the gradient, divergence, and Laplacian operators of vector calculus. Conversion of these Galilean invariant linear differential operators into Lorentz covariant differential operators is required to recast (1-2) into a form that achieves conservation of momentum and mass when the control volume is a curved spacetime modeled as a Lorentzian manifold. A fluid flowing at a relativistically significant velocity in four-dimensional spacetime has the capacity for time dilation and length contraction. For this reason it is also imperative that the Galilean invariant velocity $\mathbf{u} = u_x \hat{x}_1 + u_y \hat{x}_2 + u_z \hat{x}_3$ and external force $\mathbf{F} = F_x \hat{x}_1 + F_y \hat{x}_2 + F_z \hat{x}_3$ fields must be modeled as Lorentz covariant four-dimensional vector, or four-vector, fields [14] which have temporal components $\hat{x}_0$ as well as spatial components ($\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \hat{x}_3$) (6-7). Furthermore, the curvature of spacetime is capable of distorting even the four-velocity and four-force, so the proper time τ must be expressed in terms of the line element ds^2 of (5). The pressure and density scalar fields (8-9) must also be redefined since force, area, mass, and volume all change in the presence of high velocities or high spacetime curvature, which are both encountered in relativity.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v} : (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4 = \sum_{i=0}^3 v^i(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \hat{x}_i \\ &= \frac{c\gamma(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}} \hat{x}_0 + \frac{u_x \gamma(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}} \hat{x}_1 + \frac{u_y \gamma(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}} \hat{x}_2 + \frac{u_z \gamma(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}} \hat{x}_3, \quad |u| = \sqrt{u_x^2 + u_y^2 + u_z^2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f} : (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4 = \sum_{i=0}^3 f^i(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \hat{x}_i \\ &= \frac{\gamma(|u|, c)(\mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{u})}{c} \hat{x}_0 + \gamma(|u|, c) F_x \hat{x}_1 + \gamma(|u|, c) F_y \hat{x}_2 + \gamma(|u|, c) F_z \hat{x}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The relativistic pressure field P (8) is more complex to calculate than any other fluid mechanical quantity in our analysis because the notion of area changes as a function of both the curvature of spacetime and the direction of the force creating the pressure. To calculate the relativistic area element A_{rel} that $\mathbf{f}$ is distributed across, one must project (5) onto a plane whose normal vector is collinear with the line of action of $\mathbf{f}$. This plane, being a function only of the direction of $\mathbf{f}$, is conceived of as a two-dimensional submatrix of (5) parameterized by the coordinates (σ_1, σ_2) . The determinant of this submatrix contracted with (5) yields the area element. Since $\mathbf{f}$ is directly proportional to $\mathbf{F}$ through λ and A_{rel} is proportional to A_0 through the reciprocal of the square of γ due to length contraction, the end dependency of P on γ is cubic in nature. The quantity $|F|$ denotes the magnitude $\sqrt{F_x^2 + F_y^2 + F_z^2}$ of $\mathbf{F}$.

$$P : (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M \rightarrow \mathbb{R} = \frac{\mathbf{f}}{A_{\text{rel}}} = \frac{|F| \sqrt{g_{00}} \gamma^3(|u|, c)}{A_0 \sqrt{\left| g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x_\mu}{\partial \sigma_a} \frac{\partial x_\nu}{\partial \sigma_b} \right|}} = \frac{P_0 \sqrt{g_{00}} \gamma^3(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{\left| g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x_\mu}{\partial \sigma_a} \frac{\partial x_\nu}{\partial \sigma_b} \right|}} \quad (8)$$

The relativistic density field (9) combines the effective increase in mass as a function of the Lorentz factor at high velocities with the effective change in volume as the result of the curvature

of spacetime. The latter is a function of the volume element, which in turn is equal to the square root of the determinant of the metric tensor.

$$\rho : (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M \rightarrow \mathbb{R} = \frac{m_{\text{rel}}}{V_{\text{rel}}} = \frac{m_0 \gamma(|u|, c)}{V_0 \sqrt{-|g|}} = \frac{\rho_0 \gamma(|u|, c)}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \quad (9)$$

4.1 Recovery of Cartesian fields

The formulae (6-9) defining the four-vector and relativistic scalar unknowns of the relativistic Navier-Stokes equations in terms of their Cartesian counterparts are capable of being inverted to yield the Cartesian fields once the relativistic Navier-Stokes equations are solved. This procedure allows the four-dimensional velocity, density, and pressure fields to be projected into Cartesian space to be analyzed as the human eye would intuitively observe them.

4.1.1 Velocity and external force vector fields

Once the four-velocity $\mathbf{v}$ is calculated, inversion of (6) allows the Cartesian velocity field $\mathbf{u}$ to be recovered (10). This inversion is accomplished by equating components of $\mathbf{u}$ and $\mathbf{v}$ to generate a system of three linear algebraic equations which is easily solved via Cramer's rule.

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{c\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}(b-1)(d-1)}{abd - a - b - d + 2} \hat{x}_1 + \frac{c\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}(a-1)(d-1)}{abc - a - b - d + 2} \hat{x}_2 + \frac{c\sqrt{-\frac{ds^2}{c^2}}(a-1)(b-1)}{abd - a - b - d + 2} \hat{x}_3, \quad (10)$$

$$a = c + \frac{c}{v^1 v^1}, \quad b = c + \frac{c}{v^2 v^2}, \quad d = c + \frac{c}{v^3 v^3}$$

4.1.2 Relativistic blowup condition

There appears to exist a danger of division by zero in (10) that would produce infinite velocity in finite time over a finite distance. To refute this notion, we observe that taking the definitions of a , b , d , and γ together with (10) leads to the conclusion that (10) holds so long as the condition (11) holds, and the integrity of (11) is in turn a function of its two coefficients containing c . Analysis of the behavior of these coefficients as functions of c show that they approach positive and negative unity respectively at large c since approximations of these figures when c is taken as its accepted value of 299,792,458 metres per second are shown to have precisions on the order of one part per quintillion (12-13). This relativistic blowup condition (11) thus simplifies to (14) for nearly all practical purposes. Since both squares and sums of squares of real values are always positive, (14) remains satisfied and (10) thus holds for all $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ everywhere.

$$|\mathbf{u}|^2 + \frac{c^2 - 1}{c^2} \left((u_x u_z)^2 + (u_y u_z)^2 + (u_x u_y)^2 \right) \neq \frac{3c - 2 - c^3}{c^3} - 1 \quad (11)$$

$$\lim_{c \rightarrow 299\,792\,458} \frac{c^2 - 1}{c^2} = \frac{89875517873681763}{89875517873681764} = 1 - 1.1116525352 \times 10^{-18} \approx 1 \quad (12)$$

$$\lim_{c \rightarrow 299\,792\,458} \frac{3c - 2 - c^3}{c^3} = -\frac{6736000604343497159989635}{6736000604343497384833978} = 1.1126500561 \times 10^{-17} - 1 \approx -1 \quad (13)$$

$$|\mathbf{u}|^2 + (u_x u_z)^2 + (u_y u_z)^2 + (u_x u_y)^2 \neq -2 \quad (14)$$

4.1.3 Pressure and density scalar fields

Substitution of (10) into the formulae for relativistic density and pressure (8-9) and inverting the latter allow recovery of the Cartesian pressure and density fields (15).

$$P_0 = \frac{P \sqrt{\left| g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x_\mu}{\partial \sigma_a} \frac{\partial x_\nu}{\partial \sigma_b} \right|}}{\sqrt{g_{00}} \gamma^4(|u|, c)}, \quad \rho_0 = \frac{\rho \sqrt{-|g|}}{\gamma(|u|, c)} \quad (15)$$

4.2 Covariant derivative

4.2.1 Vectors

The covariant derivative ∇_i [15] of a four-vector $\sum_{j=0}^3 v^j \hat{x}_j$ is given by (16) and forms the foundation of all further differential operator derivations relevant to our analysis as the relativistic analogue of the gradient operator $\nabla(\cdot) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{\partial(\cdot)^j}{\partial x_i} \hat{x}_i \hat{x}_j$ in (1) where $(\cdot)$ is a scalar ($j = 0$) or a vector. We shall thus treat the relativistic covariant derivative as the philosophical equal of the classical gradient. The covariant derivative as a differential geometric construct is soundly Lorentz covariant since it is designed purposefully to account for the effects of curved spacetimes modeled as Lorentzian manifolds. The quantity Γ_{ik}^j is the Christoffel symbol of the second kind (17) [16] which contains all information about the spacetime geometry and causal structure encoded in (5).

$$\nabla_i v^j = \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^j v^k \right) \hat{x}_i \hat{x}_j \quad (16)$$

$$\Gamma_{bc}^a = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{d=0}^3 \left(g^{ad} \frac{\partial g_{bd}}{\partial x_c} + g^{ad} \frac{\partial g_{cd}}{\partial x_b} - g^{ad} \frac{\partial g_{bc}}{\partial x_d} \right) \quad (17)$$

4.2.2 Scalars

The covariant derivative of a scalar quantity ϕ , such as the pressure and density fields or the divergence of a vector field, simply equals the sum of partial derivatives (18) of ϕ because the lack of indices in the latter cancels the Christoffel symbols in (16). The result of the cancellation of the Christoffel symbols is that the Lorentz covariant version of the pressure gradient in (1) remains unchanged from its Galilean invariant counterpart with the exception of an addition of a time derivative component. The presence of a time derivative of pressure assists with the difficult task of temporally advancing the pressure during computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analyses to remain in step with the temporal evolution of $\mathbf{u}$.

$$\nabla_i \phi = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i} \hat{x}_i \right) \quad (18)$$

4.3 Divergence

4.3.1 Vectors

The divergence ∇_j of a contravariant vector field v^j is given (19) by the trace of the covariant derivative of v^j and is the curved-space analogue of the divergence $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial u^i}{\partial x_i}$ of the Cartesian velocity field $\mathbf{u}$ in (1-2) [17]. (19) is required to construct a Lorentz covariant continuity equation since its Galilean invariant counterpart (2) depends almost entirely on the divergence operator and is equally crucial to construct the viscous terms of (1). The notation $|g|$ denotes the determinant of (5), which ensures Lorentz covariance by its careful handling of the volume element.

$$\nabla_j v^j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (19)$$

4.3.2 Second-rank tensors

The divergence of a second-rank tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ is given by (20). The difference between (19) and (20) is that (20) is a vector, which is also known more generally as a first-rank tensor, as opposed to (19) which is a scalar or zeroth-rank tensor. It is critical to ensure correct associations between components of tensors of various ranks when encountering the latter in linear combinations such as our relativistic version of (1) to avoid algebraic contradictions, bearing in mind that taking the divergence of an n th-rank tensor generally produces an $(n-1)$ th rank tensor. Taking the covariant derivative (16) of an n th-rank tensor likewise produces an $(n+1)$ th-rank tensor.

$$\nabla_j T^{ij} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} T^{ij})}{\partial x_i} \right) \hat{x}_j \quad (20)$$

4.4 Material derivative of the four-velocity field

The material derivative (21) of a four-vector v^j is likewise defined as the dot product of (6) with its own covariant derivative (16), where v^j denotes proper time. In a relativistic fluid dynamics context, proper time corresponds to the time experienced by a fluid parcel as it travels along its worldline [18]. Since (6, 16) are Lorentz covariant, (21) is also Lorentz covariant.

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}}{D\tau} = v^i \cdot \nabla_i v^j = \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left(v^i \frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^j v^i v^k \right) \hat{x}_j \quad (21)$$

4.5 Laplace-Beltrami operator

Combining the definitions of scalar gradient (18) and vector divergence (19) into the definition $\nabla^2 \phi = \text{div}(\text{grad } \phi)$ of the Laplacian operator ∇^2 yields the Laplace-Beltrami operator (22) applied to a scalar field ϕ , which generalizes the Cartesian Laplace operator $\nabla^2 \phi = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x_i^2}$ to curved spacetime and remains Lorentz covariant so long as $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of a Lorentzian manifold. Since we have assumed (5) that M is indeed Lorentzian, it follows that (22) is Lorentz covariant.

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \nabla_j \cdot (\nabla_i \phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_j} \right) \right) \quad (22)$$

5 Construction of Lorentz covariant momentum and continuity equations

Since there are now four components of velocity (6) and external forces (7), there must also be four components of momentum. We now turn our attention to assembling the four-momentum equations which constitute the bulk of our proposed model of relativistic viscous flow. It is clear from (1) that a Navier-Stokes momentum equation must include a material derivative to account for acceleration, a viscous term to account for internal resistance to flow, a pressure term providing the internal stresses which cause and sustain the flow, and an external forcing term to account for other forces acting on the fluid and thus influencing the flow. In keeping with this heuristic layout of fluid momentum conservation, the derivation of the general Lorentz covariant momentum equation (23) invokes (18) to formulate the scalar pressure four-gradient, (21) for the material derivative of velocity, and (16-17, 19-20) for the viscous term. The positions and purposes of all the aforementioned correspond to their Cartesian equivalents as written in (1).

5.1 Compressible momentum equations

Changing all gradient and divergence operators in (1) to covariant derivatives (16, 19) and curved-space divergence operators (19) in (1) respectively produces the general form of any of the four momentum conservation Navier-Stokes equations for relativistic compressible flow (23). We shall now fully expand all summations to set aside all ambiguity. Note that the second viscous term of (1) which contains a transpose of the velocity field is written as a covariant derivative whose component index i has been raised to denote transpose by exchange of its two summation indices.

$$\frac{Dv^j}{D\tau} = v^i \cdot (\nabla_i v^j) = f^j - \frac{\nabla_i P}{\rho} + \nu \nabla_j \left(\nabla_i v^j + \nabla^i v^j - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla_j v^j \mathbf{I}) \right) + \zeta \nabla_i (\nabla_j v^j) \quad (23)$$

5.1.1 Viscous terms

Due to the complexity of the viscous terms of (1) in the case of compressible flow, it serves best for the clear articulation of the mathematical nature of the relativistic version of the Navier-Stokes momentum equations to treat the derivation of the viscous terms separately. Their core is formed by the sum S_j (24) of the covariant derivative (9) of the four-velocity, the transpose (11) of the same when it is treated as a matrix, and a column vector whose four identical components equal the negative of two thirds of the divergence of the four-velocity.

$$S_j = \nabla_i v^j + \nabla^i v^j - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla_j v^j \mathbf{I}) = \frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \left(\Gamma_{ik}^j v^k + \Gamma_{jk}^i v^k \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial \left(\sqrt{-|g|} v^l \right)}{\partial x_l} \right) \quad (24)$$

Taking the divergence of (24) and multiplying the result by ν yields all kinematically viscous terms. Taking the covariant derivative of the divergence of the four-velocity, multiplying by ζ , and subtracting this result from the total (25) yields all viscous terms.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nu \nabla_j \left(\nabla_i v^j + \nabla^i v^j - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla_j v^j \mathbf{I}) \right) + \zeta \nabla_i (\nabla_j v^j) = \\
& \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial S_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \zeta \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) \hat{x}_j \quad (25)
\end{aligned}$$

Expansion of S_j and the full formulation of all viscous terms of (23) is achieved (26) by substituting (24) into (25). Upon close examination of the indicial patterns in (26), it is evident that the Laplace-Beltrami operator is encoded within the summations to account for many of the second derivatives of the four-velocity components.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \nu \nabla_j \left(\nabla_i v^j + \nabla^i v^j - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla_j v^j \mathbf{I}) \right) + \zeta \nabla_i (\nabla_j v^j) = \\
& \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} \left(\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{k=0}^3 (\Gamma_{ik}^j v^k + \Gamma_{jk}^i v^k) \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^l)}{\partial x_l} \right) \right) \right) + \\
& \zeta \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) \hat{x}_j \quad (26)
\end{aligned}$$

5.1.2 Lorentz covariant compressible Navier-Stokes momentum equations

Substituting (26) into (23) and expanding the material derivative per (21) yields the four momentum equations (27-30) which constitute the relativistic analogue of (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{Dv^0}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^0 v^i v^k \right] = f^0 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_0} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_0} \left(\frac{\zeta}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) + \\
& \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} \left(\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{k=0}^3 (\Gamma_{ik}^0 v^k + \Gamma_{0k}^i v^k) \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^l)}{\partial x_l} \right) \right) \right) \hat{x}_0 \quad (27)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{Dv^1}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^1 v^i v^k \right] = f^1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\zeta}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) + \\
& \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} \left(\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_1} + \sum_{k=0}^3 (\Gamma_{ik}^1 v^k + \Gamma_{1k}^i v^k) \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^l)}{\partial x_l} \right) \right) \right) \hat{x}_1 \quad (28)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{Dv^2}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^2 v^i v^k \right] = f^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\zeta}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) +$$

$$\frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} \left(\frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_2} + \sum_{k=0}^3 (\Gamma_{ik}^2 v^k + \Gamma_{2k}^i v^k) \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^l)}{\partial x_l} \right) \right) \right) \hat{x}_2 \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dv^3}{D\tau} &= \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^3 v^i v^k \right] = f^3 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_3} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3} \left(\frac{\zeta}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) \right) + \\ &\frac{\nu}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sqrt{-|g|} \left(\frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial x_3} + \sum_{k=0}^3 (\Gamma_{ik}^3 v^k + \Gamma_{3k}^i v^k) \right) - \frac{2}{3} \sum_{l=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} v^l)}{\partial x_l} \right) \right) \right) \hat{x}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

5.2 Incompressible momentum equations

Incompressible flow assumes $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial(\dots)} = \zeta = 0$. While these conditions are effective in simplifying (1-2), the relativistic dependency of ρ on the velocity through γ prevents ρ from being truly constant even if ρ_0 is constant. Therefore we must introduce a concept of "relativistic compressibility" since there exist conditions under which ρ is treated as a constant and (1-2) reduce. Even if ρ is not absolutely constant, it is capable of being effectively constant in its influence on the flow. If such is the case, the flow in question is relativistically incompressible.

Because relativistically incompressible flows feature constant ρ and zero ζ , the viscous terms in (23) reduce to the Laplace-Beltrami operator applied to the four-velocity field as the divergence of the four-velocity vanishes. The general form of the j th momentum equation, or the j -component of the four-momentum balance vector equation of which (1) is the Cartesian analogue, is given by (31) which is derived by the same relativistic modifications as (23).

$$\frac{Dv^j}{D\tau} = v^i \cdot (\nabla_i v^j) = f^j - \frac{\nabla_i P}{\rho} + \nu \nabla^2 v^j \quad (31)$$

5.2.1 Relativistically incompressible Navier-Stokes momentum equations

Substituting (18, 21-22) into (31) yields the four momentum equations (32-35) which constitute the relativistic analogue of (1) for the case of $\frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial(\dots)} = \zeta = 0$.

$$\frac{Dv^0}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^0 v^i v^k \right] = f^0 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_0} + \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left[\frac{\nu \frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x_j})}{\partial x_i}}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \right] \hat{x}_0 \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{Dv^1}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^1 v^i v^k \right] = f^1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} + \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left[\frac{\nu \frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_j})}{\partial x_i}}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \right] \hat{x}_1 \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{Dv^2}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^2 v^i v^k \right] = f^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} + \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left[\frac{\nu \frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_j})}{\partial x_i}}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \right] \hat{x}_2 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{Dv^3}{D\tau} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left[v^i \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_i} + \sum_{k=0}^3 \Gamma_{ik}^3 v^i v^k \right] = f^3 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_3} + \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 \left[\frac{\nu \frac{\partial (\sqrt{-|g|} g^{ij} \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_j})}{\partial x_i}}{\sqrt{-|g|}} \right] \hat{x}_3 \quad (35)$$

5.3 Continuity equation

5.3.1 Systemic determinacy and Lorentz covariance by relativistic compressibility

Substituting the definition of the divergence (19) into the continuity equation (2) yields the Lorentz covariant Navier-Stokes continuity equation written with inverse metric tensor components for both the compressible (36) and incompressible (37) cases. There are now five relativistic Navier-Stokes equations (32-35, 37) with five unknown quantities $\{v_0, v_1, v_2, v_3, P\}$ given an external force field $\mathbf{f}$ and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of M which constitute a closed second-order system of nonlinear PDEs in the incompressible case. For the compressible case (27-30, 36), an equation of state is needed to close the system. Since each term in (27-30, 32-37) is Lorentz covariant, and (27-30, 32-37) are composed of sums of such terms, the system in both cases is proven Lorentz covariant by the linearity of (4).

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-\det(g)}} \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-\det(g)} \rho v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x_0} \quad (36)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial (\sqrt{-\det(g)} v^i)}{\partial x_i} \right) = 0 \quad (37)$$

5.3.2 Increase in notational size

After the product rule is applied to simplify the advective, viscous, and continuity terms, the total number of individual terms rises by 746.6 percent from 30 terms in the Cartesian formulation of (1-2) to 224 terms in (23-27) for the incompressible case. For the compressible case, the termwise increase is 4,812.5 percent from 40 Cartesian terms to 1,925 terms in (19-22, 28).

6 Validation by Galilean reduction

We test our theory of relativistically compressible (27-30, 36) and relativistically incompressible (32-35, 37) flow by imposing constraints on v , M , and $g_{\mu\nu}$ which reflect the spatiotemporal circumstances when γ is small and thus reduce (27-30, 32-35, 36-37) to the Cartesian coordinates $M = \mathbb{R}^4 \implies g_{\mu\nu} = \mathbf{I}_4$ of (1-2). The next constraint is to downgrade the four-velocity field to a Cartesian vector field $\mathbf{v} : (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) \in M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ by taking the limit $c \rightarrow \infty$ which results in $\gamma \rightarrow 1$, reducing M to Galilean invariance. The entirety of (27, 32) along with all Christoffel symbols in all instances of (16) vanish and all instances of the metric tensor determinant equal unity. Since time dilation is no longer present, time proper τ equals the local coordinate time x_0 per (3). While there may seem to exist a contradiction that the cancellation of v^0 does not necessarily result in the cancellation of $\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_0} \mid j \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,3]}$, the dependency of the definition of the material derivative (21) on that of the covariant derivative (16) which includes $\frac{\partial v^j}{\partial x_0} \mid j \in \mathbb{N}_{[0,3]}$ as well as the treatment of

$\mathbf{v}$ as a Cartesian vector field $\mathbf{u}$ allows the latter to remain intact as (1) would impose for the case $M = \mathbb{R}^4 \implies g_{\mu\nu} = \mathbf{I}_4$.

6.1 Compressible flow

All of the above constraints together reduce (27-30, 36) to (38-41), which match (1-2) in three-dimensional rectangular coordinates. This seamless reduction from definition on a Lorentz manifold to definition on a Cartesian domain supports the validity of (27-30, 36).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dv_1}{Dx_0} &= \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_3} = f^1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_3^2} \right) + \\ &\quad \left(\zeta + \frac{\nu}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_1 \partial x_3} \right) \hat{x}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dv_2}{Dx_0} &= \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_3} = f^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_3^2} \right) + \\ &\quad \left(\zeta + \frac{\nu}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_2 \partial x_1} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_2 \partial x_3} \right) \hat{x}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dv_3}{Dx_0} &= \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_3} = f^3 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_3} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_3^2} \right) + \\ &\quad \left(\zeta + \frac{\nu}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_3 \partial x_1} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_3 \partial x_2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_3^2} \right) \hat{x}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v^1)}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial(\rho v^2)}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial(\rho v^3)}{\partial x_3} = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x_0} \quad (41)$$

6.2 Incompressible flow

All g^{ij} in the Laplace-Beltrami viscous terms of the incompressible momentum equations (32-35) cancel for any $i \neq j$ and collapse into sums of second partial derivatives of the velocity component associated with each momentum equation when $i = j$, equaling the Laplacian operator in the nonrelativistic and incompressible version of (1). The Christoffel symbols in the material derivative also cancel due to the cancellation of all derivatives of the metric tensor components. These two major reductions produce Cartesian versions (38-40) of (32-35). The divergence operator in the continuity equation (37) is rendered Cartesian (45) by the reduction of the metric tensor determinant to unity. As with the compressible case (38-41), this seamless reduction of (32-35, 37) from a Lorentz manifold domain to a Cartesian domain (42-45) supports the validity of (32-35, 37).

$$\frac{Dv_1}{Dx_0} = \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_3} = f^1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_1} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^1}{\partial x_3^2} \right) \hat{x}_1 \quad (42)$$

$$\frac{Dv_2}{Dx_0} = \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_3} = f^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_2} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^2}{\partial x_3^2} \right) \hat{x}_2 \quad (43)$$

$$\frac{Dv_3}{Dx_0} = \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_0} + v^1 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_1} + v^2 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_2} + v^3 \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_3} = f^3 - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_3} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v^3}{\partial x_3^2} \right) \dot{x}_3 \quad (44)$$

$$\frac{\partial v^1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial v^3}{\partial x_3} = 0 \quad (45)$$

7 Conclusion

A Lorentz covariant version of the Galilean invariant Navier-Stokes equation set was successfully derived for a Newtonian fluid flowing on a Lorentzian manifold and all fields were proven to be convertible to their nonrelativistic forms with neither loss of information nor generality. The Lorentz covariant equation set reduces neatly to the familiar Galilean form of the Navier-Stokes equations upon the imposition of a Cartesian metric tensor and velocity field. This reduction does not require a laborious recasting of the covariant derivative or any other operations of differential geometric tensor calculus. These findings are expected to make progress toward a mathematical theory of relativistic viscous fluid motion in curved spacetime which is compatible with major results such as the Einstein field equations, geodesic equations, and relativistic Euler equations.

Combining this work's findings with more nuanced results such as the equations of motion through spacetime described by black hole vacuum solutions, as well as a hopeful future generalization to non-Newtonian and magnetohydrodynamic flows when coupled with the Einstein-Maxwell equations, could assist in the modeling of astronomical phenomena such as black hole accretion disks, relativistic jets, and stellar winds. The use of the Robertson-Walker metric has potential for CFD studies of cosmological evolution. The Navier-Stokes equations are also now capable of being written down in arbitrary coordinate systems which need not necessarily be orthogonal. The ubiquity of the Laplacian in mathematical and theoretical physics, including quantum mechanics, has the potential to seed, for example, the investigation of quantum field theory in curved space by generalizing the Schrödinger equation to curved space via the Laplace-Beltrami operator.

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